

e-ISSN: 3048-9733

Volume 08 Issue 02
May-Aug, 2026

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YOLO-Driven Image Based Automated Attendance System for Smart Classroom

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ABSTRACT

Due to the limitations of traditional roll-calling and biometric techniques for attendance recording, the system is difficult to adapt for large classrooms and wasting the time of teachers and students. We propose a YOLO based image driven automated attendance system for smart classrooms in this paper. In this paper, the YOLOv8 object detection algorithm is used for face detection in real-time, and the Video- based under the topic Face. By the use of a camera, the system takes classroom pictures, analyzing them with use of computer vision, and then records attendance automatically in a centralise database. The framework consists of six parts: image capturing, image preprocessing, face detection, face recognition, database management, and a web-based application to view attendance logs. The proposed system differs from traditional systems in that it increases efficiency, decreases attendance fraud, and eliminates the need for human interaction. The code is written in Python and makes use of OpenCV, YOLOv8, Face Recognition libraries, and MySQL database. The deliverable includes increased accuracy, attendance tracking in real-time, lower paperwork burden, protected-data storage, and scalable implementation within educational institutions. This framework facilitates classroom automation and plays a role in the digital transformation of intelligent educational environment.

Keywords:-*YOLOv8, Face Recognition, Attendance System Automation, Computer Vision, Deep Learning, Real Time Object Detection*

1. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring attendance is essential for academic participation and compliance in schools and universities. Conventional means of taking attendance, such as calling out the roll, are time-consuming and subject to human error. Biometric systems, although automated, involve a certain degree of physical touch and individual validation, which cause waiting lines and raise hygienic issues. With the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Computer Vision (CV) techniques, the image based attendance systems came out as a viable solution. They rely on facial recognition to identify students and take attendance without any physical contact.

In this work, we propose YOLO based automated attendance system which is based on YOLOv8 (You Only Look Once version 8) that a state-of-the-art object detection algorithm, to identify faces in real-time. Face recognition model then encodes the facial features and compares it with the existing student records in the database.

The architectural design of the system includes:

- Camera Module (Image Acquisition)

- Preprocessing Module
- YOLO Face Detection
- Face Encoding & Recognition
- Attendance Database
- Web Dashboard Interface

This system prevents proxy attendance, saves time and has precise digital records. It supports real-time surveillance, centralized management, and is well suited for smart classrooms.

2. OBJECTIVES

- Keywords: attend, monitoring, on time, the system monitoring the system to investigate the attendance in our class.
- To study and implement YOLOv8 for detecting faces in real-time.
- To implement a deep learning based face recognition system.
- To propose and implement an automated attendance marking system.
- To integrate a system with centralized database.
- To assess the performance of the system in a real classroom environment.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sr. No.	Paper Title	Publisher & Year	Methodology	Limitations
1	“You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection”	IEEE CVPR, 2016	Introduced YOLO for real-time object detection using single CNN.	Not optimized specifically for face recognition.
2	“Rapid Object Detection Using a Boosted Cascade of Simple Features”	IEEE CVPR, 2001	Used Haar Cascade for fast face detection.	Low accuracy under lighting and pose variations.
3	“DeepFace: Closing the Gap to Human-Level Performance”	IEEE CVPR, 2014	Applied deep CNN for high-accuracy face verification.	Requires large dataset and high computation.
4	“Dlib-ml: A Machine Learning Toolkit”	JMLR, 2009	Provided facial landmark detection and encoding tools.	Depends on pre-trained models; scalability issues.

5	“Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition”	IEEE CVPR, 2016	Introduced ResNet for deep feature extraction.	Complex architecture; high training cost.
6	“Eigenfaces for Recognition”	Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience, 1991	Used PCA-based face recognition method.	Sensitive to lighting and facial variations.
7	<i>Deep Learning</i> (Book)	MIT Press, 2016	Explained CNN, optimization, and representation learning.	Theoretical; not application-specific.

4. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig.1:-System Architecture of YOLO-Driven Image Based Automated Attendance System for Smart Classroom

5. EXPECTED OUTCOMES

The YOLO-based IBAS that we propose would help in streamlining the time consumptive process of whole class attendance. The system can recognize several students at the same time by combining real-time face detection with deep learning based face recognition using YOLOv8. It minimizes the manual intervention and also removes the proxy attendance with a trust-able biometric validation. The system guarantees rapid response processing even when the classroom is full. The attendance is securely recorded in a centralized database, which can then be easily accessed and used to generate reports. The web-based attendance board facilitates to keep a close eye on the attendance for the faculty members. The solution is scalable, cost-effective, and suitable for deployment in smart classrooms. It can automate, accuracy and record digitally in education institutions.

The expected outcomes are:

- High Accuracy Detection
- Real Time Attendance Marking
- Multi Student Recognition
- Reduced Proxy Attendance
- Automated Report Generation
- Secure Centralized Database
- Web-based Dashboard

Monitoring Dataset:

- Student Face Images(30 –40 images per student)
- Stored as encoded

Embeddings Features:

- Live camera feed
- Automatic attendance logs
- Admin control panel

6. CONCLUSION

The YOLO-based Image processing AAS is an intelligent and efficient attendance

management system compared with the traditional attendance management. By utilizing YOLOv8 for live face detection, deep learning for recognition, the system accomplishes precise and automatic attendance logging. It reduces human manual work, avoids proxy attendance and boosts digital management of the class. The overall solution is high-performance and scalable, makes it perfectly fit for running in today's smart education industry.

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